

Supplemental Material for

**Compartmentalized Cell Envelope Biosynthesis
in *Mycobacterium tuberculosis***

Julia Puffal^{a,1}, Ian L. Sparks^{a,1}, James R. Brenner^a, Xuni Li^{b,c}, John D. Leszyk^{b,c},
Jennifer M. Hayashi^a, Scott A. Shaffer^{b,c}, and Yasu S. Morita^{a,2}

a. Department of Microbiology, University of Massachusetts, Amherst, MA 01003, USA

b. Department of Biochemistry and Molecular Pharmacology, University of Massachusetts
Medical School, Worcester, MA 01605 USA

c. Mass Spectrometry Facility, University of Massachusetts Medical School, Shrewsbury, MA
01545 USA

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Table S1

Legend for Dataset S1

Figure S1. LC-MS quantification of phosphatidylethanolamine content in membrane fractions. **A.** Density gradient and protein concentration profile of sucrose gradient fractions of *M. tuberculosis* cell lysate. IMD (fractions 3-6), 1.08-1.11 g/ml; PM-CW (fractions 8-12), 1.13-1.17 g/ml. **B.** LC-MS quantification of phosphatidylethanolamine (PE) 34:1 and PE 35:0. Values represent the percentage of the total combined normalized peak area for each individual lipid species that was measured in each fraction.

Figure S2. Evaluation of cell-free PPM biosynthesis. Crude lysates of *M. smegmatis* and *M. tuberculosis* were radiolabeled with GDP-[³H]-Mannose. Lipids were extracted, partially purified, and analyzed by HPTLC.

Figure S3. PyrD-2xHA-tagRFP, expressed from the endogenous locus, showing the IMD association. **A.** Sucrose gradient density fractionation of *M. tuberculosis* strain where the endogenous *pyrD* gene was replaced with *pyrD-2xHA-tagRFP*. Sucrose density and protein concentration for each fraction are shown. IMD (fractions 3-6), 1.08-1.11 g/ml; PM-CW (fractions 8-12), 1.13-1.17 g/ml. **B.** Immunoblot showing the IMD localization of PyrD-2xHA-tagRFP (68.2 kDa). MptC, PM-CW marker (47 kDa). Experiments are repeated twice and representative results are shown.

Figure S4. The IMD association of Psd-mNeonGreen-HA. **A.** Density gradient and protein concentration profile. IMD (fractions 3-6), 1.08-1.11 g/ml; PM-CW (fractions 8-12), 1.13-1.17 g/ml. **B.** Immunoblotting of Psd-mNeonGreen-HA (53.5 kDa). MptC, PM-CW marker. **C.** SIM images of log phase cells. Experiments are repeated twice and representative results are shown.

Table S1. Primers to create plasmids used in this study.

Plasmid	Gene ID	Protein	Forward Primer	
			Reverse Primer	
pMUM036	Rv2139	PyrD	A161	ATCCATATGTATCCCCTGGTGGT
			A162	ACTGCTGGGTTGCCGACGTCTT
pMUM145	Upstream of Rv2139	PyrD knock-in	A536	TTTTTTTTCCATAGATTGGCACAAAGTTGGTTTTCGCCGTG
			A537	TTTTTTTTCCATATTTTGGATTAATGCTGGGTTGCCGACGTCTT
	TagRFP		A557	TTTTTTTTTATAATTACCCGTACGACGTCCCGGACTACGCGTACCCGTACGACGTC
			A558	TTTTTTTTCTTAAGCTTGTAGAGCTCGTCCATGCC
	Downstream of Rv2139		A538	TTTTTTTTCCATAATTTGGCTTAAGTAAAGCGCTAACGCTGCTCG
			A539	TTTTTTTTCCATCTTTTGGATACAAGGCCAACGTCGTCC
pMUM215	mNeonGreen	Psd-mNeon Green	A483	ACTCTTAAGATGGTTAGTAAAAGAGAAGA
			A484	ACTGTTAATTAACAATTGTTGTAGAGCTCATCCATGCCA
	Rv0437c		A630	TTTTTTTTTCATATGGTGGCCAGACGCCCCCGC
			A631	TTTTCTTAAGCAATTGTCGACATTCGGCCAGCACGG
pMUM222	Rv3808c	GlfT2	A628	TTTTTTTTTCATATGATGAGTGAAGTCCGCGC
			A629	TTTTCTTAAGCAATTGGCCATGCTCGGGCTCT
pMUM257	Rv2955c	Rv2955c	A849	TTTTTTTTTCATATGCAGTTCCAAGATGTGCCCGC
			A850	TTTTTTTTCTTAAGTCCCTCCGGCTCGGAATAAAGA
pMUM258	Rv2957	Rv2957	A851	GTGGCAGAAAAGACGTCCGA
			A852	CACGTCGTAGTAGAGCGAGAACT

Dataset S1. List of proteomic hits in the IMD and the PM-CW. Table legends are at the bottom of each spreadsheet. The “PM-CW” and “IMD” spreadsheets list proteins enriched 2-fold or more relative to each other, as determined by Mann-Whitney Test. The “IMD (IP)” spreadsheet lists proteins that were enriched in the IMD immunoprecipitated by PyrD-HA in comparison to a negative control (wildtype lysate not expression PyrD-HA). The “IMD (both)” spreadsheet lists proteins that were found in both “IMD” and “IMD (IP)”. The “IMD (all)” spreadsheet is the compiled list of all proteins that were found in either “IMD” or “IMD (IP)”.